

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KODJO****FIRST NAME: TCHIOFFO****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Literature review (EUCLID 2019, 17)
2. Critical thinking (EUCLID 2019, 2)
3. Creative thinking (EUCLID 2019, 2)
4. In-text citations (EUCLID 2019, 6)
5. Turabian and Chicago style (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
6. World English (EUCLID 2019, 27)
7. Large collective nouns (EUCLID 2019, 29)

WRITING AN ACADEMIC ESSAY: THE EUCLID BLUEPRINT

1) INTRODUCTION

The coursepack for ACA-401/ACA-401D period one (1) is a comprehensive set of materials that explain academic essay writing for Euclid University masters and doctoral programs. A PDF document and a Youtube video provided guidance to students on the best practices for academic essay writing using the UK or preferably US English. Coming from Cameroon, English and French have always been at the center of the education system. Although I initially went to francophone primary and high school, my university choices led me to do a Master in Global Studies at Leipzig University entirely taught in English. That program helped me master the basic principles of academic writing for political science and international relations. During those two years, academic writing used either APA or Chicago style. In EUCLID programs, Turabian style, a subset of the Chicago style, is the recommended approach. Also, I learned practices and tools such as Zotero that bolster the productivity and quality of my essays.

2) TOPIC RESEARCH AND LITERATURE REVIEW

EUCLID (2019, 2) explains that academic writing does not occur in a knowledge void. As such, it lives in the backdrop of previous works and sometimes borrows from them to improve knowledge production (ibid.). Therefore, authors are encouraged to put aside "plenty of time" to properly understand the research topic and acquaint themselves with various perspectives and school of thoughts (ibid.). Topic research "provides the knowledge and evidence" that is vital to produce the central thesis and arguments that will help solve the research question (ibid.).

To prepare for essay writing, students must ask many questions, especially regarding their level of knowledge of the research question, state of the art in the field, and the usefulness of reading materials to support an argument or the thesis (ibid.). While reading, students are encouraged to make notes or to highlight "relevant information" as well as to "copy down the bibliographic details" of all reading materials thesis (ibid.).

What I found encouraging is that EUCLID has equipped us with tools that can help to grab bibliographic details such as Zotero. Besides, I use Adobe Acrobat DC to read PDF materials. It helps to underline information that I find useful to make sense of the course material. Also, EUCLID provides valuable techniques to collect relevant information and skip insignificant materials. For example, students are encouraged to use the table of contents to get an overview of the material content and locate essential data points or arguments.

However, I find it awkward and quite misleading that the literature review, which is the underlying purpose of topic research, is not mentioned in this section but rather kept in a separate chapter four. Also, chapter four does not discuss literature review but rather grammatical and syntactical rules to be used to write good academic essays.

For Boote and Beile (2005, 3), a brilliant literature review is a "precondition" to design original research. In that vein, Boote and Beile (2005, 7) developed a "framework" to analyze the quality of literature reviews in doctoral essays. The framework uses criteria, namely coverage, synthesis, methodology, significance, and rhetoric, to assess literature reviews (Boote and Beile 2005, 7-9).

Coverage examines how the literature review includes or excludes research materials and the criteria used by the author to justify the choice (Boote and Beile 2005, 7). Conditions to assess the coverage of a literature review entail "topicality, comprehensiveness, breadth, exclusion, relevance, currency, availability, and authority" (ibid.).

Synthesis evaluates the ingenuity used to position critical arguments of the research documents in the literature review (ibid.). Synthesis is the capability to place the research in the historical trajectory of the field (ibid.). It makes clear the scope of existing works and also the fluidity and richness of the vocabulary (Boote and Beile 2005, 8).

The methodology assesses the various methods used in the field (Boote and Beile 2005, 7). It evaluates the benefits and drawbacks of each methodological approach as well as their popularity in the literature. It also considers the attractiveness of each methodology to solve specific research questions and how it influences research findings (Boote and Beile 2005, 8).

Significance is concerned with the practicalities, ambiguities, and shortcomings of existing research and its implications for the research question (Boote and Beile 2005, 9). Rhetoric focuses on examining the coherence and logical structure of the literature review (ibid.). The rhetorical sophistication and organization are a vital part of a well-written essay (ibid.). For students, they are "key determinants in how influential and persuasive readers believed the review to be" (ibid.).

3) CREATIVE THINKING IN ACADEMIC WRITING

According to EUCLID (2019, 2), academic essay writing "requires both creative and critical thinking." Critical thinking focuses on the processes and principles to follow and apply from starting the essay to its submission (ibid.). Creative thinking, on the other hand, promotes thinking out of the box and broadening the perspectives used to evaluate the research question (ibid.).

What I found interesting in this section is the notion of creative thinking. While researching the topic, EUCLID (2019, 2) advises that "creative thinking encourages you to broaden your ideas." To accomplish it, "techniques like brainstorming or mind-mapping" can be leveraged to look at the topic from different angles (ibid.).

It is quite practical since mind-mapping is known to improve "the learning capacity in terms of the number of ideas generated and improves writing focus" of authors and researchers" (Mahmud, Rawshon, and Rahman 2011, 22). Mahmud et al. (2011,24) suggest that mind-mapping is a powerful tool to organize and link ideas in a graphical manner to reveal hidden connections and unpack concealed or original perspectives. For them, maps are easier to understand, retain, and recall for most people and provide a componentized visualization of topics that stimulates "deep learning" (Mahmud et al. 2011, 22-24).

According to Rawlinson (2017, 2), brainstorming is the "best and most widely used" creative thinking technique. The education system creates psychological barriers that force people to think only logically and analytically and prevent them from using their creative potential (Rawlinson 2017, 2-3). However, at the expense of solo brainstorming, Rawlinson discusses group brainstorming sessions exclusively in large organizations under manager supervision (Rawlinson 2017, 3).

De Bono (2009, 5-7) argues that creative thinking is not only a desirable aptitude that is natural or instigated using some "vague exhortation." He contends that creative thinking should be a deliberate and well-structured process and advocates for what he labeled "lateral thinking" De Bono (2009, 7). For him, "vertical thinking" is only concerned with "proving or developing" ideas, while "lateral thinking" is a process to reorganize those

ideas to generate new ones. As such, "lateral thinking" is a beneficial process, and De Bono (2009,13) provides a set of learnable techniques to tap into our cognitive potential and spur creative thinking.

4) PLAGIARISM AND REFERENCING

EUCLID (2019,5) describes plagiarism as the act of not "giving credit to the author" of any source information used in the essay that is not an original idea of the writer. As such, plagiarism is qualified as "wrong and unethical" and a "serious academic offense" (EUCLID 2019, 4-5).

Therefore, students should cite and reference all material used in the course of their academic essay writing. Citations and references should follow a proper structure based on the Turabian format when writing in-text citations, quotations, paraphrases, and footnotes and references (EUCLID 2019, 8-10). Also, signal phrases are essential to introduce quotations or paraphrases (EUCLID 2019, 10). From my previous experiences, especially during my Master in Global Studies, I was already exposed to APA and Chicago style. Given that Turabian is a subset of the Chicago style, I am not new to writing papers using that format.

The aspect that I found essential in this part of the course pack is the importance of plagiarism in the EUCLID curriculum. Also, I found useful EUCLID fundamental rule to identify common knowledge is to verify that information is repeatedly and readily available in the literature (ibid.).

Plagiarism is a notion that has been assessed by various authors, and many perspectives have emerged. For example, Halak and El-Hajjar (2019, 200–201) have studied two prevention techniques: "assigning individual coursework specifications" and "using individual presentation" for engineering classes at the University of Southampton. They also examined two detections techniques, more explicitly detecting the "writing style" and "testing software" for engineering students (Halak and El-Hajjar 2019, 203–5).

For plagiarism prevention, Halak and El-Hajjar (2019, 201–202) found that assigning individual coursework reduced the "inter-report similarity scores" obtained from Turnitin antiplagiarism software. They also discovered that using personal presentation affects student[s]" views of plagiarism" and normalizes marks distribution (Halak and El-Hajjar 2019, 201–202). For plagiarism detection, they established that in addition to using antiplagiarism software like Turnitin, identifying writing styles discrepancies can help spot plagiarized paragraphs Halak and El-Hajjar (2019, 204). More interestingly, for software classes, they could test the code to detect anomalies in the "report produced for each code and more precisely by considering the run time of the code, the length of the code, and the commenting style" Halak and El-Hajjar (2019, 205).

Some authors are more philosophical and consider plagiarism a blurry phenomenon. In "Plagiarism and Inspiration," Rosen (1980, 87) explores the "influence of Plato on Lafontaine." For Rosen (1980, 87-88), accusations of plagiarism against

Lafontaine do not hold ground simply because Plato inspired him to the point that he becomes natural "not to quotation but original thought."

He adds that there is a fine line between influence and plagiarism (Rosen 1980, 87). For him, plagiarism focuses exclusively on "ethics and law" at the detriment of creativity (Rosen 1980, 88). Duncan (2015) concurs that many artists are "blurring the line between influence and plagiarism." They do not remember plagiarizing because influences are unintentional and may etch a song in their subconscious (Duncan, 2015).

5) ENGLISH VARIATIONS IN ACADEMIC WRITING

English is the most widely spoken and most used language in international literature. Two linguistic variants, namely American and British English, dominate and shape the language. However, American English has made tremendous strides since the end of the second world war (EUCLID 2019, 27). Therefore, it has become "the dominant influence on "world English" "due to many factors, including the size and wealth of the US and its central position in international affairs (ibid.).

Though American and British English are very analogous, they may diverge at many levels, notably pronunciations, spelling, vocabulary, meaning, grammar, syntax, grammar, punctuations, usage, and connotations (EUCLID 2019, 27-35).

I found it interesting to learn the intricacies of the American and British English, especially the differences in usage of "large collective nouns." I found the American English to be more natural in using the verb "has" instead of "have" in British English as described in the sentence "Finnair has a flight to London today" (EUCLID 2019, 29). In the "politically correct" section, I cannot fathom why saying "African Americans" is more accurate than "black Americans" (ibid.). Yet, I support that "Stay-at-home mom" is more precise than "housewife" (EUCLID 2019, 32).

Also, I did not understand the necessity of discussing "ethnolects," especially the "Black English" or the "Yiddish or Ethnic Jewish" English (ibid.). For me, explaining that ethnic background or origin shapes English and produces very original lexical and structural terminologies is sufficient. In all cases, it was captivating to dive into the subtle yet marked deviations between American and British English.

6) CONCLUSION

The first coursepack material provided a detailed and insightful introduction to academic writing for the Ph.D. program in Diplomacy and International Relations.

Even though I am not new to academic writing, I learned new perspectives, techniques, and tools that add value to my academic writing skills. I also learned that the program is quite demanding, especially in terms of the number of papers to produce for

each course. The greatest challenge was to make sense of the coursepack when its structure was not evident, and various connected notions appear disconnected from each other.

In all cases, I was able to make sense of the reading material and use Zotero to build my bibliographical database and write in-text citations. It is a handy tool that alleviates the burden of writing down the bibliography and managing sources inside Microsoft Word. As I move forward with the course, it has become central in my academic writing toolkit.

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